

Ensemble vs splice-aware (SpliceAI/Pangolin) and conservation comparators: AUPRC and lower-bound PP3 strength

Deep intronic (splice-mediated)
n=6180, 402 P/LP

Merged UTR (non-splice)
n=2644, 24 P/LP

Identical gnomAD-covered subset per region (the only reachable SpliceAI/Pangolin source); labels give the ACMG PP3 strength assigned from the lower 95% CI bound.